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Ref: Ares(2025)3424102 - 28/04/2025
PROSPLIGN

Prospecting natural lignin biodiversity towards unlocking value-added bioactive motifs and molecules

The PROSPLIGN project has received funding from the Horizon Europe Programme of the European Union under Grant Agreement n° 101135298.

WP2

KELADA

D2.4 – Summary Report on Sourcing and characterisation of lignin for bioprospecting

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	101135298	Acronym	PROSPLIGN	
Full Title	Prospecting natural lignin biodiversity towards unlocking value-added bioactive motifs and molecules.			
Start Date	01/01/2024	End Date	31/12/2026	
Project Website	prosplign.eu			
Deliverable	D2.4 - Summary Report on Sourcing and characterisation of lignin for bioprospecting			
Work Package	WP2 – Sourcing and Characterisation of biomass for lignin bioprospecting			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	30/04/25	Actual	25/04/25
Type	Report	Dissemination Level		PU
Lead Beneficiary	KELADA			
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Document History

Version	Issue Date	Description	Contributor
0	05/03/2025	Deliverable outline drafted	Malachi Gillick-Healy (KelAda)
0.1	28/03/2025	Intermediate draft	Malachi Gillick-Healy (KelAda)
0.2	10/04/2025	Advanced draft	Malachi Gillick-Healy (KelAda), Luis Olaechea (BFH)
0.3	16/04/2025	Full draft	Malachi Gillick-Healy (KelAda), Luis Olaechea (BFH)
0.4	16/04/2025	DCE Committee check	Filippo Giancarlo Martinelli (Magfi), Malachi Gillick-Healy, Arlene Bonner (KelAda)
1.0	25/04/2025	Coordinator approval	Malachi Gillick-Healy (KelAda)

List of Beneficiaries

#	Participant (organisation name)	Acronym	Country	EU	Type
1	KelAda Pharmachem	KELADA	Ireland	Yes	SME
2	University of Helsinki	UH	Finland	Yes	UNI
3	Fundación Medina	MEDINA	Spain	Yes	RPO
4	NOVA University of Lisbon	NOVA	Portugal	Yes	UNI
5	University College Dublin	UCD	Ireland	Yes	UNI
6	MAGFI Ltd	MAGFI	Malta	Yes	SME
7	Bern University of Applied Sciences	BFH	Switzerland	No	UNI

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
IP	Intellectual Property
WP	Work Package
SEN	Sensitive (referring to confidential project deliverables)
MTA	Material Transfer Agreement
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
GPC	Gel Permeation Chromatography (used for molecular weight analysis)
NMR	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
HSQC NMR	Heteronuclear Single Quantum Coherence NMR (for lignin linkage analysis)
³¹ P NMR	Phosphorus-31 NMR (used for hydroxyl group quantification)
FTIR	Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (functional group analysis)
M _n	Number-average molecular weight
M _w	Weight-average molecular weight
Đ	Dispersity (molecular weight distribution)
β-O-4	A key aryl ether linkage in lignin structure

1 Executive Summary

The **PROSPLIGN** project seeks to unlock the untapped potential of lignin, a complex and chemically diverse aromatic natural polymer isolated from lignocellulosic biomass. Traditionally treated as a low-value byproduct from industries such as pulp and paper, lignin is now being re-evaluated in PROSPLIGN as a novel resource for the discovery of bioactive molecules with applications in pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and fragrances. Unlike conventional approaches that aim to simplify lignin into a narrow set of aromatic chemicals for bulk applications, PROSPLIGN embraces its natural complexity, leveraging innovative chemical and enzymatic methods combined with high-throughput bioactivity screening to identify novel bioactive molecules from lignin.

This public report provides an overview of PROSPLIGN's **lignin sourcing and characterisation strategies**, which are critical to ensuring a diverse and high-quality lignin supply for downstream workflows. Key aspects include:

- **Diverse Sourcing Strategy:** **KELADA** coordinated the procurement of lignin samples from suppliers all over Europe derived from multiple plant types (hardwood, softwood, and grass) and extraction methods (organosolv, enzymatic, kraft, etc.), prioritising extraction techniques known to preserve lignin's native structure and key features associated with bioactivity.
- **Quality Validation:** Advanced analytical techniques—including **GPC, 2D HSQC NMR, ³¹P NMR, and FTIR**—were employed by **BFH** to assess lignin properties such as molecular weight, chemical composition, and solubility, validating their suitability for PROSPLIGN's lignin depolymerisation and bioactivity screening workflows.
- **Key Findings:**
 - Lignin's structural diversity is highly dependent on both its **botanical origin** and **extraction conditions**, with a wide variety of features identified in the lignins sourced in the project.
 - Even within lignins obtained from the same extraction method, variations in processing conditions significantly impact lignin qualities.
- **Risk Mitigation:** Challenges such as supplier reliability, IP conflicts, and cost constraints were addressed through diversified sourcing, small-scale sampling, and careful negotiation of Material Transfer Agreements.

By establishing a robust framework for lignin sourcing and characterisation, PROSPLIGN lays the groundwork for discovering high-value bioactive compounds from a natural renewal resource, contributing to the transition toward a circular bioeconomy and creating new market opportunities for lignin valorisation.

2 Introduction

2.1 Overview of the PROSPLIGN Project

PROSPLIGN aims to bioprospect within lignocellulosic biomass, the most abundantly available terrestrial natural resource, specifically focusing on its largely underutilised lignin fraction. Lignin is a structurally complex and chemically diverse natural polymer, with its composition varying significantly depending on both the plant source and the extraction method used to obtain it. It is important to highlight that lignin is not a single substance, but rather **lignin is a vast family of chemically diverse natural polymers**. Lignin's complexity is often seen as a challenge as conventional lignin valorisation approaches aim to "simplify" lignin into a few well-defined fractions for bulk industrial applications. In contrast, PROSPLIGN embraces lignin's complexity as an opportunity to prospect a largely untapped resource for novel bioactive molecules with potential applications in pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and fragrances.

Traditionally, lignin has been considered a byproduct of industries like pulp and paper, where it is often burned for energy – however, more recently lignin has been highlighted as a natural source of aromatic chemicals and recognised as a feedstock for the production of renewable chemicals or fuels.¹ While lignin has been used as a resource for developing biobased platform chemicals to be used in the synthesis of bioactive molecules,² PROSPLIGN leverages lignin's chemical diversity for a previously unmet application: **bioprospecting—the search for new bioactive compounds**. To unlock lignin's bioactivity potential, PROSPLIGN is developing an innovative approach that combines cutting-edge chemical and enzymatic methods with advanced statistical analysis and high-throughput detection techniques. This integrated strategy aims to unlock the bioactivity potential of lignin and lay the foundation for new valorisation opportunities for lignocellulosic biomass. By developing sustainable and efficient ways to unlock lignin's potential, PROSPLIGN contributes to the broader shift towards a bio-based circular economy.

¹ Brienza, F.; Cannella, D.; Montesdeoca, D.; Cybulska, I.; Debecker, D. P. A Guide to Lignin Valorization in Biorefineries: Traditional, Recent, and Forthcoming Approaches to Convert Raw Lignocellulose into Valuable Materials and Chemicals. *RSC Sustainability* **2024**, 2 (1), 37–90. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3SU00140G>.

² (a) Lan, W.; Luterbacher, J. S. A Road to Profitability from Lignin via the Production of Bioactive Molecules. *ACS Cent. Sci.* **2019**, 5 (10), 1642–1644. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscentsci.9b00954>. (b) Afanasenko, A. M.; Wu, X.; De Santi, A.; Elgaher, W. A. M.; Kany, A. M.; Shafiei, R.; Schulze, M.; Schulz, T. F.; Hauptenthal, J.; Hirsch, A. K. H.; Barta, K. Clean Synthetic Strategies to Biologically Active Molecules from Lignin: A Green Path to Drug Discovery**. *Angewandte Chemie* **2024**, 136 (4), e202308131. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ange.202308131>. (c) Park, J.; Kelly, M. A.; Kang, J. X.; Seemakurti, S. S.; Ramirez, J. L.; Hatzell, M. C.; Sievers, C.; Bommarius, A. S. Production of Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients (APIs) from Lignin-Derived Phenol and Catechol. *Green Chem.* **2021**, 23 (19), 7488–7498. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1GC02158C>.

A key challenge is that the chemical structure of lignin after separation from lignocellulosic biomass is significantly influenced by the extraction process applied to it. For example, the widely used kraft process, which removes lignin during paper production, alters its chemical structure substantially, which may affect its suitability for bioprospecting.³ PROSPLIGN addresses this by sourcing lignin from a wide range of extraction methods, prioritising those that preserve key structural features which are particularly important for the enzymatic and chemical lignin depolymerisation methods being developed in PROSPLIGN to selectively release bioactive molecules from lignin. Realising this potential requires i) a **targeted sourcing strategy** by KELADA to obtain lignin with desirable and diverse properties and ii) **advanced characterisation techniques** by BFH to assess its quality and provide a common baseline for the lignins used in PROSPLIGN's workflows.

2.2 Objectives of this Report on Lignin Sourcing and Characterisation

This summary report – available to the public – provides an overview of PROSPLIGN's approach to **lignin sourcing and characterisation**, summarising the strategies used to obtain diverse lignin samples, and the methods applied to assess their quality. Sourcing lignins from various plant sources and extraction methods amplifies the number of distinct and chemically diverse lignins which can be screened in PROSPLIGN's workflows, thereby enhancing the potential for discovery of commercially valuable bioactive molecules and achievement of PROSPLIGN's objectives.

More detailed and comprehensive details on the lignin sourcing and characterisation activities (particularly commercially sensitive aspects related to PROSPLIGN's data and lignin suppliers) have been reported separately in sensitive (SEN) deliverables. A comprehensive review comparing both well-known and newly emerging extraction methods and how they affect lignin from different plant types has been reported in deliverable **D2.1 "Report on lignin natural biodiversity"** (SEN) submitted at Month 6. We have prepared a detailed report outlining the analytical methods used to validate the quality of sourced lignin and a preliminary overview of the lignin analyses performed to date – these details are included in deliverable **D2.3 "Preliminary report on Lignin quality validation"** (SEN) submitted at Month 7. We have also prepared a preliminary report outlining the methodologies and commercially sensitive aspects

³ Obrzut, N.; Hickmott, R.; Shure, L.; A. Gray, K. The Effects of Lignin Source and Extraction on the Composition and Properties of Biorefined Depolymerization Products. *RSC Sustainability* **2023**, *1* (9), 2328–2340. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3SU00262D>.

involved with Task 2.2 “Sourcing of Relevant Selected Lignin” – these details are included in deliverable **D2.2 “Preliminary Report on Lignin Sourcing and Options”** (SEN) submitted at Month 9.

3 Approach to Lignin Sourcing

3.1 How Lignin is Sourced in PROSPLIGN

We have sourced lignin derived from various plant species and extraction methods to supply a diverse range of substrate types for the enzymatic and chemical depolymerisation activities in WP3. The chemical structure of lignin varies substantially depending on the plant source and extraction method used to obtain it. Understanding the relationship between the characteristics of various lignin types and how they will perform in PROSPLIGN’s workflows is integral to optimising the desired outputs of this project.

The ideal set of lignin samples to be sourced for PROSPLIGN should represent the broadest possible variety of chemical diversity. To achieve this, we set out to obtain samples derived from a range of different plant species and which have been extracted using various methods. Most of the lignin produced industrially is via extraction methods such as Kraft or acid hydrolysis which tend to be harsh and yield lignin that is often condensed and/or chemically modified. Obtaining samples from large commercial producers of lignin obtained is the most straightforward. On the other hand, it has been more challenging to establish supply of lignin from producers who use emerging cutting-edge extraction methods (such as enzymatic, organosolv, or ionosolv extraction methods) as they are often at research or pilot scale (i.e. not yet commercially operative or widely practiced).

The most common limitation we have encountered has often been negotiation of mutually acceptable Material Transfer Agreements with suppliers, this process was sometimes lengthy, however in all cases was fully resolved. Large commercial organisations shared lignin samples easily, however smaller organisations developing cutting-edge extraction methods at pilot scales (producing the most attractive lignin for PROSPLIGN) often required more detailed IP discussions and compensation to provide lignin samples.

3.2 Key Considerations for Selecting Lignin

Our understanding of the lignin production landscape and quality validation process have been leveraged to define the various aspects of our lignin sourcing methodology outlined below.

The summary of the key factors we will consider when sourcing lignin includes:

- **Extraction Method.** We are prioritising lignin extracted using milder methods which retain the lignin's native structure and desirable profiles of chemical bonds . Lignin from harsher methods is lower priority as they tend to produce heavily condensed lignin with low chemical diversity, however lignin extracted from these methods are being investigated in PROSPLIGN's workflows to ensure a comprehensive comparison can be made.
- **Quality Parameters.** The ideal lignin must have high purity, desirable molecular weight, and its chemical complexity preserved. Lignin with optimal quality parameters will be prioritised to maximise the widest variety of chemical fragments (and therefore bioactivity potential) which could be derived from lignin.
- **Supplier Identification.** The industrial lignin production landscape is mostly made up of kraft and liginosulfonate processes, which are less desirable for our project due to heavy condensation and lack of chemical diversity. Meanwhile the processes producing higher quality lignin are all performed only up to pilot scale (see Deliverable D2.1 for more details). Therefore, our priority has been to identify producers of technical high-quality lignin throughout Europe.
- **Sample Acquisition:** Small samples (10-100g) are requested initially which is sufficient for the initial development stages of the project. Depending on how various lignin types perform in WP3 (Lignin depolymerisation) and bioactivity results in WP4 (Bioactivity Screening, Fractionation, Isolation, Characterisation), we will obtain larger quantities scaling up to 1kg-scale if the lignin proves suitable.

The outputs of PROSPLIGN's workflows are aimed at creating innovative IP that has the potential to significantly enhance the demand for lignin produced by various suppliers. As the project matures, the novel methodologies developed for the selective depolymerisation of lignin and the identities and bioactivity profiles of lignin-derived compounds will form the foundation of new IP arising from the project. In turn, this IP will have the potential to i) drive demand for and ii) creation of markets for specific types of lignin, particularly those which best perform in PROSPLIGN's innovative workflows – in particular lignin with high technical purity and preserved native chemical structure.

- **Freedom to Operate.** A primary focus at this stage of the project is to secure a stable supply of quality lignin, allowing the consortium the freedom to operate and experiment without infringing on existing IP rights. The project's success depends on our ability to freely explore, test, and optimise methods applied to different lignin sources without compromising the consortium's rights to protect IP related to the liberated bioactive compounds or the methods used to achieve their liberation. To this end, all sourcing agreements will be drafted to ensure that the consortium retains the necessary freedoms to experiment while preserving our right to protect commercially sensitive information arising from the project.

- **Compliance with IP Provisions.** Where in place, Material Transfer Agreements (MTA) or Non-disclosure agreements (NDA) with suppliers will strictly adhere to the IP provisions outlined in the grant agreement. This will include clear definitions of the consortium's rights to any IP generated during the project, while also respecting the IP rights of the lignin suppliers.
- **Adherence to Regulations:** The project will comply with EU regulations and the Nagoya Protocol to prevent biopiracy and ensure ethical sourcing.

3.3 Challenges and Considerations in Sourcing

There are several risks associated with lignin sourcing which have been identified, however effective and realistic mitigation plans have been devised in each case.

- **Risk 1: Insufficient or unreliable supply of lignin**
 - *Mitigation 1:* To mitigate the risk of an insufficient or unreliable lignin supply, we will identify multiple suppliers for various lignin types. By diversifying our supplier base, we reduce the dependence on any single source and ensure a steady supply throughout the project.
- **Risk 2: Insufficient chemical diversity or bioactivity profiles**
 - *Mitigation 2:* To address the potential lack of chemical diversity or bioactivity in the lignin samples, we will source lignin from a wide range of plant types and extraction methods. This approach maximises the likelihood of discovering bioactive compounds with diverse chemical properties, enhancing the project's overall success.
- **Risk 3: High production costs for lignin suppliers**
 - *Mitigation 3:* Acknowledging that some suppliers may face high production costs, we will request smaller lignin sample sizes which they can accommodate for low/no cost. These smaller samples will be sufficient for initial depolymerisation screenings to identify samples which produce promising bioactive mixtures. When a particular depolymerised lignin sample produces strong results in bioactivity screenings, we will negotiate with the supplier to produce larger quantities, ensuring budget efficiency and focusing resources on the most promising samples.
- **Risk 4: Irreconcilable IP conflicts between suppliers and PROSPLIGN's grant agreement**
 - *Mitigation 4:* In the event of IP conflicts that prevent us from obtaining lignin samples, we will have alternative suppliers lined up. By maintaining a growing network of potential suppliers, we will minimise the risk of IP conflicts and secure

the necessary variety of lignin samples, therefore ensuring that the project can continue productively without interruption.

3.4 Results of Lignin Sourcing

An analysis of the number of countries, plant species/types, and extraction methodologies represented through the sourced lignin samples is outlined below in **Table 1**.

Table 1 - Summary of details represented by the array of lignin samples sourced in PROSPLIGN

Item	Quantity
Lignin samples sourced	30
Countries sourced from	6
Feedstock species	13
Hardwood lignins	18
Grass lignins	6
Softwood lignins	4
Lignin extraction processes	5

4 Lignin Characterisation and Key Findings

4.1 Summary of Characterisation Methods Used

To accurately capture the structural and chemical complexity of lignin, BFH employed a multi-technique approach consisting of the most advanced and widely used lignin analysis methodologies⁴:

- **GPC (Gel Permeation Chromatography):** Enabled quantification of number-average (Mn) and weight-average (Mw) molecular weights, as well as dispersity (Đ). Primarily used to validate the mass profile of the sourced lignins, GPC was also useful for tracking

⁴ Liu, J.; Li, X.; Li, M.; Zheng, Y. Chapter Six - Lignin Biorefinery: Lignin Source, Isolation, Characterization, and Bioconversion. In *Advances in Bioenergy*; Li, Y., Zhou, Y., Eds.; Elsevier, 2022; Vol. 7, pp 211–270. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.aibe.2022.05.004>.

changes to lignin following lignin oxidation in Task 3.2; and the chemical (Task 3.3) and enzymatic (Task 3.4) lignin depolymerisation activities.

- **^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR (2D Heteronuclear Single Quantum Coherence NMR spectroscopy):** ^1H - ^{13}C HSCQ NMR offers high-resolution mapping of carbon-hydrogen correlations, making it possible to quantify and distinguish between various interunit linkages (β -O-4, β -5, β - β , etc.). The fundamental chemical groups (units) of lignin – syringyl, guaiacyl, and p-hydroxyphenyl – can be easily identified, as well as other chemical features such as p-coumarates, ferulates, tricin, fatty acids or even residual sugars. HSQC NMR allows the semi-quantification of chemical groups and linkages in lignin based upon their relative abundance to total aromatics present in the lignin. This method is extensively used for lignin analysis and many examples can be found in literature.
- **^{31}P NMR (Phosphorus NMR spectroscopy):** Following phosphorylation with a suitable reagent (e.g., TMDP), this technique quantifies hydroxyl groups by type (aliphatic OH, condensed phenolic OH, non-condensed phenolic OH, and carboxylic acids). It provides a robust and sensitive measure of the syringyl, guaiacyl and hydroxyphenyl structures present at the terminal branches of lignin polymers.
- **FTIR (Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy):** While FTIR provides lower resolution data compared to the abovementioned methods, it is cheaper, faster and provides qualitative insights into the presence of characteristic functional groups such as carbonyls, aromatic rings, and ether linkages. Thanks to the simplicity and low cost of FTIR measurements, this method can be used for fast screening of different lignins and is used in PROSPLIGN to quickly evaluate and compare lignins and depolymerised lignin mixtures.

4.2 Key Findings on Lignin Composition and Properties

The most striking findings from the analyses of the lignins used in PROSPLIGN are as follows:

1. **Greater structural diversity than expected:** Even among lignins of similar botanical origin, substantial variation in interunit linkage composition, functional group content, and molecular weight profile was observed.
2. **Strong dependency on extraction method:** Lignins isolated via different extraction methods (e.g., kraft, soda, organosolv) showed significant differences between them.
3. **Even stronger influence of extraction conditions:** Lignins obtained from the same extraction method (e.g., organosolv) but with variations in temperature, solvent composition, acidity, and reaction time, had markedly different properties. To illustrate the impact of harsher extraction conditions on lignin, the HSQC NMR spectra displayed in **Figure 1** compares two beech (hardwood) lignins extracted under mild (L03_01) and standard conditions (L03_02). The HSQC spectra of lignin L03_01 (Figure 1A) and lignin

L03_02 (Figure 1B) reveals well-defined cross-peaks in both lignins corresponding to similar syringyl (S_{2,6}, S'_{2,6} and S''_{2,6}) and guaiacyl (G₂, G₅, G₆) content. Meanwhile in the spectrum for lignin L03_02 (extracted under relatively harsher conditions) we can see the cross-peaks corresponding to condensed syringyl and guaiacyl groups (labelled as S_{cond} and G_{cond}) which are absent in the spectrum of than mild-extracted lignin L03_01. Further evidence of the impact of harsher extraction conditions on lignin condensation are also observable in the oxygenated aliphatic region of the HSQC spectra for L03_01 and L03_02 (Figure 1C and 1D, respectively) as the relative abundance of β-O-4 ether bonds is significantly lower in L03_02 than for L03_01.

Figure 1: HSQC spectra of lignins L03_01 (A, C) and L03_02 (B, D) with corresponding chemical features highlighted (right).

5 Conclusion and Outlook

The **PROSPLIGN** project represents a unique thematic shift in lignin valorisation, moving beyond traditional bulk applications to explore its potential as a biodiscovery resource for novel **bioactive molecules**. This report highlights the project's approach to sourcing and characterising lignin, ensuring a chemically diverse, well-defined and high-quality supply for the downstream depolymerisation and bioactivity screening activities.

Key aspects include:

- **Strategic Sourcing:** By prioritising lignin extracted via methods which preserve chemical diversity and securing samples from a wide range of plant species, PROSPLIGN maximises the likelihood of discovering novel bioactive molecules from lignin.
- **Advanced Characterisation:** A multi-technique analysis approach revealed that lignin's properties are profoundly influenced by extraction methods and conditions, underscoring the need for careful selection to preserve desirable structural features.
- **Overcoming Challenges:** Through proactive risk management—including supplier diversification, phased sampling, and IP-compliant agreements—the project has successfully secured a representative lignin library while maintaining budget and operational flexibility.

Looking ahead, the insights gained from lignin characterisation will inform the **optimisation of depolymerisation workflows** in Work Package (WP) 3, promoting the efficient discovery of bioactive compounds in WP4, and further validation of commercial potential of novel bioactive molecules in WP5. As PROSPLIGN progresses, the project is positioned to demonstrate lignin's potential as a renewable feedstock for high-value applications, stimulating innovation in areas such as lignin valorisation and drug discovery - supporting the broader transition to a bio-based economy.

By bridging the gap between lignin's natural complexity and its untapped potential as a biodiscovery resource, PROSPLIGN not only advances scientific understanding, but also paves the way for new commercial opportunities in the sustainable use of biomass resources.